

Psycho-Social Analysis of Organizational Efficiency of Managers and Staff

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To cite this article: Merve Atalay, Current Science, Volume 4, No. 8-4, 2022, p. 108 – 133. - 0099-0001-2208-0105.

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ISSN: 2667-9515

Barcode: 977266795001

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- The magazine is published monthly.

"The magazine will be at the subscriber's address in the first week of the month." ("Scientific Studies – Current Science Georgia")

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Abstract

The interaction between the components in the organization and the person doing the work results in the working conditions that are the product of this interaction. In other words, working conditions can be defined and researched not only according to human qualities, but also according to the characteristics existing within the organization. Research in occupational health psychology has historically taken an individual approach that focuses on measuring and interpreting at the individual level. Some empirical data accumulated in recent years suggest that working conditions differ systematically from one organization to another. It has played a dominant role in the empirical studies conducted in the field. The job demands and competencies model is a situational framework that emphasizes the impact psychosocial factors play in the work environment. To be more specific, they are conceptualized as aspects of the work environment that affect people around the core ideas of demand and control. On the other hand, the method by which it was decided makes it unclear to what extent the model is truly situation oriented. While mostly activated by evaluating workers' responses to questions about the conditions of their jobs, this strategy has been for placing greater emphasis on individual differences in feelings rather than actual differences in the jobs themselves and contributing to the individualization of structural elements of the work environment. A different approach to dealing with these issues has been to use a classification system based on the occupations of the persons concerned. People tend to view occupations as uniform social structures made up of individuals whose authors are the respective rights holders.

Keywords: *Organization, Organizational Psychology, Organizational Sociology, Organizational Efficiency, Work and Work Psychology, Efficiency, Sociology*

1. Introduction

Bolin et al. / the impact on the psychological and social aspects of the organization's working conditions, partly because of the nature of the work carried out. For example, if we know anything about baking, then we also know something about a baker's working conditions (skilled but repetitive work with direct and appreciated interactions with customers). However, measurements are made at the individual level unless the specific organizational or structural characteristics of the job are considered. Even in these circumstances, the assessment of individuals' feelings of their work or organization may be the main data being evaluated. Specifically, this information should focus on the extent to which individual feelings of model components reflect aim differences between organizations. It is a particular social environment that allows for the implementation of preventive actions if it can be shown empirically that organizations differ in their components. In addition, if certain levels can be found within the organizational structure, where its components are constantly fluctuating, it will be able to direct interventions to these specific levels to reduce the impact of the workload. The purpose of this research is to explore the extent to which organizations have an impact on business demands and control modeled by the model .

Also, one of the aims is to explore the impact of various levels of the organization on job demands and control, and more specifically to decide which level of the organization is most important in terms of the two dimensions. Analysis at many levels is the basis for multilevel thinking, the concept of people interacting with the social environments to which they belong. When analyzing working conditions from a multi-level perspective, it is necessary to consider how activities occurring at various levels of an organization affect the working conditions of individuals. Organizations are multidimensional and have varying degrees of hierarchical levels because this

reflects the structures of organizations themselves. Especially in larger companies, there may be more than one level of organization capable of influencing one's working conditions. These levels may include the top management of a corporate conglomerate, a specific institution, or even the working group of large multinational companies. They may also include a study group. Multi-level modeling makes it possible to clarify the size of differences between organizations as well as differences between organizations by separating variance from individual reports of stressors and moderators according to the level from which they originate, such as an individual, workgroup, or organization.

This can be done by comparing the results of different organizational levels. In the workplace, most multilevel analyzes of data at two or more levels have been done to explore the importance of interaction at the individual and group level. Studies on topics such as workload and support, and effectiveness and social interaction between leadership and staff are examples of the types of research that fall into this category. Organizational factors influencing demand and control have an extreme but significant impact on workers' health, according to the findings of a Swedish study of human service businesses . A Dutch study of bank employees used multilevel analyzes to explore the impact of workplace pressure on employee health.

The findings showed that job demands, and levels of control should be understood as having both social and individual roots. Another study conducted on employees of health institutions in the Netherlands came to remarkably similar conclusions. These examples also show that various units within the business, such as departments within banks or retail firms , and sub-units, such as wards in hospitals, are selected to function as representatives of the institution.

2. People in the Organization Category

Most of the research focused on the study of people in a single organizational category, collecting data only on individuals and combining individual data to be the organization. In other cases,

primitive proxies were used to be forms of establishment, such as the size and age of the establishment. This may be the reason there is no well-defined and all-encompassing definition of organization that can be used in research investigating the impact of organizations on working conditions. It may also explain why so little is known about the broad relationship between organization and working conditions. However, only a handful of multilevel studies used a population of organizations and collected data at the organizational level.

The impact of both organizational changes and the industry's working conditions on Härestam et al. and Van Veldhoven et al., examining specific relationships between psychosocial work conditions and work-related tension and well-being, exemplified in these studies. Here are two examples of studies that give an idea of such relationships. Both studies used an organizational example that was cross-sectional in nature. Harenstam et al. the organization handles anything between 9 and 66 percent of the variation in individual employment conditions. Vanveldhoven et al. Using aggregated individual information, he found that organization handled about 9 percent of variation in tension and about 12 percent of variation in well-being. In this study of several types of organizations, it is also important to explore the various levels of formal organization in the organizational charts of participating organizations. This allowed us to explore the size of organizational impact on business demands and control and to examine whether it can be generalized across diverse types of organizations.

psychological stressors (i.e., workload), are imposed on the employee in the working situation. The other main dimension in the original model is control, which refers to the degree of autonomy available to the worker to mitigate the effects of demands. The two components that make up the control dimension are decision authority and effective use of skills. The first term refers to decision-making authority, the ability of an individual to use their full capabilities, while the next term refers to opportunities for that person to do so. Due to the interaction between the two main dimensions of job demands and job control, there are four diverse types of jobs (high-voltage jobs, low-voltage jobs, active jobs, and passive jobs). Each of these jobs is distinguished by a particular

exposure that can have either healthy or unhealthy effects on the individual. The model runs on the assumption that people with the same type of jobs are exposed to the same level of stress. Although environmental factors are emphasized in the model, the working situation is considered as an interaction between the causes arising from the environment and the causes arising from the person. According to the model, job demands, and control are assumed to be a multilevel phenomenon decided by both organizational and individual factors. This is the case because it is specified in the model. The formal structure of an organization is intricately linked to both the needs of the business and the control exercised over it. A network of positions, each occupied by a particular person, forms the formal structure. Each position in the company is entrusted with a specific set of responsibilities and has varying degrees of power. The way the division of labor and co-ordination of authority is organized decides whether positions are specialized with easy tasks completed under time constraints, or whether positions are standardized with tight performance control. In other words, the way roles are arranged within an organization's formal structure is a crucial factor in deciding which of the four employment categories a person can hold. As a result, work redesign is recognized as a successful preventive technique for improving work-related health rather than individual prevention efforts.

Components and procedures information had two diverse sources of data: one about organizations and one about people working for those organizations. The information was collected as part of a larger follow-up study designed to explore the relationship between certain occupational risk factors and health in a large group of businesses. Individual data were supplemented with information on organizations in later analyses. A two-stage sampling was used as this is what Kalleberg suggested. As a first step, organizations that have a contract with an occupational health service (OHS) were asked to take part in the research.

3. Applying the Same Criteria to Organizations

classified each response to ensure that the same criteria were applied to all organizations . After the interview, the researchers talked about the findings to make sure they were all on the same page. In the rare cases where the research team and the administrator questioned had differing views on the classification of an individual response, the research team came to a firm choice. This is a choice that is in any case confirmed by the administrator in question. When the two interviewers could not agree on anything, a third person from the working group was brought in to help and majority rule was used to decide how to act. Each manager questioned was given a written summary of the interview for their own reference. Information that was initially unclear or incomplete was later clarified over the phone. The primary organizational unit explored for this study is the organization elsewhere defined as "the specific , identifiable and physical space in which commenters are actually employed". This was the primary organizational unit investigated for this study. We based our definition of "organization" on Kalleberg and Marsden's use of comparative organization studies.

Each of the selected organizations was subjected to a comprehensive analysis to find similar organizational units and levels. To measure the degree of establishment in the institutions taking part in the study, we considered three criteria of the official establishment. To get started, the unit needed to have a manager responsible for personnel, production, and budgeting needs, as well as create a separate cost unit. Large companies have dispersed as these criteria can already be met at the departmental level. By our criteria, these departments were on par with the smaller firms included in our sample. Some examples of these institutions are elderly homes, bakeries, and libraries. Second, most businesses were branches of larger organizations such as companies, hospitals, or municipal authorities . This was the case for most companies. Organizations often belonged to the same large organization, as in most cases. Information on this formal organizational level above the organization level is included in the data hierarchy so that the assumption of independence between units is not violated. This level is found above the establishment level.

As a result, most businesses have been restructured to have multiple subdivisions, each reported to the same auditor. In other words, in some organizations, individuals are nested within smaller units, and this formal level below the organizational level is eventually included in the data hierarchy and labeled as a "subunit".

Also, the data hierarchy included a level below the organizational level, called "individual". Because the supervisor is given only partial authority over production, personnel, and finance, it does not meet our requirements to be considered a subunit-level institution.

4. Success Rate

According to the findings of the research, only 3,000 of the 30,000 products that manufacturers put on the market every year are successful (Hamel, 2006). Similarly, in the study conducted by Castellion and Markham (2013), it was revealed that the success rate of the products sold by the enterprises running in the production sector did not exceed twenty percent. Although production companies spend more than twenty million dollars on the presentation of their products, success rates are said to be between 15 and 20 percent, respectively (Perreault et al., 2013). In other words, only 10-20 percent of new products entering the manufacturing sector can compete successfully in the market each year. This results in hundreds of billions of dollars being wasted on items that fail on a global scale. The main reasons for this are the problems that arise within the organization with both leadership and knowledge and knowledge sharing (Frackenpohl et al., 2016; Knies et al., 2016; Onesto, 2017; Ritala et al., 2015).

A leader's effectiveness decides whether an organization's goals are achieved in a way that is consistent with its vision and mission. At the same time, the sense of satisfaction gained in communication between employees and managers is important both for the achievement of goals and the satisfaction of the relevant parties (Cooper & Nirenberg, 2004). Indicators of employee

dissatisfaction within leadership are the primary method of deciding a leader's effectiveness, particularly through employee attitudes and feelings based on multiple criteria :

- *The level of meeting the expectations and needs of the followers by the leaders,*
- *The ability to improve the quality of work life and the skills of the followers,*
- *Ability to contribute to the psychological development of followers,*
- *Followers' respect and gratitude to their leader,*
- *Beliefs about the integrity of leaders,*
- *The willingness and commitment of the leader to fulfill a request,*
- *absenteeism, leaving work,*
- *Do not complain,*
- *Means of slowing down and sabotaging (Yukl, 2013).*

5. The Most Important Factors in the Information Exchange Process

It is said that the most crucial factors in the information exchange process in businesses are people and individual information (Nonaka & Takeuchi, 1995). The information management process in each company is conducted by its own structure; however, information exchange is the focus of all these operations. Knowledge sharing is the primary driver of knowledge creation within an organization (Msrdal, 2006), and knowledge creation in a business is primarily the result of knowledge sharing. In today's world, the creation and sharing of knowledge in businesses is a critical factor for the success of businesses. The organization needs information to develop new goods or find solutions to problems that already exist in the business. For businesses to sell their goods successfully, they must be able to quickly generate knowledge and use specialized knowledge. As a result of the continuous learning efforts of the employees with the intention of developing and producing new business practices, the knowledge sharing skills of the employees are developed. According to Taş (2011) many scientists are of the opinion that such behavioral

changes are necessary for the implementation of new practices in the workplace. In fact, the high performance of an employee depends on the level of commitment to the company, the intensity of his emotions and the intensity of his impulses. If an employee is satisfied with his position, it is reasonable to expect him to perform well in his role. It is assumed that businesses will experience sustained growth if both their internal and external efforts to reward employees are innovative and demand the development of new talent. This is motivated by the desire to foster the creativity of the workforce (Jung et al., 2003). Making the performance of the employee permanent as well as the performance is essential and one of the strategies that can be used to make the performance permanent is the use of an effective performance evaluation. As a result, the study focused on white-collar workers employed in manufacturing enterprises. This was done because of the many product innovation activities taking place in the manufacturing industry. Job performance, firm strategies, and firm performance were all considered dependent variables, while leadership activity was considered an independent variable and knowledge-sharing behavior was considered interchangeable. The purpose of this research is to decide the existing relationships between these variables.

6. Effectiveness of Leadership in Literature

Yukl (2013) defines leadership as "the process of facilitating individual and collective efforts to understand and influence people what needs to be done and how, and to achieve shared goals". Leadership is defined as "the process of understanding and influencing people to understand what to do and how to do it, and to achieve common goals". According to Chemers (two thousand), leadership can be defined as "the process of social influence that a person can use to obtain the help and support of other people to achieve a common goal". A leader's productivity is decided by certain personal and interpersonal characteristics as well as numerous factors within the job. When it comes to being a good leader, it is important to make the kind of effort that requires you to sacrifice yourself to help your business. Employees may be motivated by the behavior of leaders

in companies and attach importance to the activities of these leaders to shape the goals they set for themselves. In general, the actions and behaviors of good leaders have a large and beneficial effect on the people they lead and on the social systems in which they run.

Jobs by the head of the organization, including quitting work, and the benefits resulting from this behavior, led to increased attention paid to research by researchers (Avolio & Locke, 2002; Choi & Mai -Dalton, 1999; de Cremer & Van Knippenberg, 2002; Yorges et al., 1999).). Effective leadership creates a high degree of dedication and motivation among employees, proves a willingness to make personal sacrifices, and is expected to instill an urge to work hard while achieving elevated levels of performance (Lowe et al., 1996). The effectiveness of a leader is measured by their capacity to create a broad-mindedness for the future of the organization, to ensure that the members of the organization focus on this goal, and to show their commitment to the organization (Conger, 1999). To begin with, one of the simplest ways to prove the value a person has for the success of a company is to prove a willingness to make personal sacrifices (Jacobson & House, 2001).

7. The Leader's Sacrifice for the Organization

Choi and Mai-dalton (1998) defined leadership effectiveness as the leader's self-sacrifice for the organization, the prevention of personal attention in the division of labor, the provision of a welfare environment in the organization, and the increase in employees' desire to stay in the organization. These are the four pillars that make up effective leadership. It is obvious that the leader is concerned about the well-being of the organization when he makes personal sacrifices for the cause (Prapavessis & Carron, 1992). Thus, altruism not only has short-term and immediate beneficial consequences for the functioning of the organization, but also has a long-term impact in keeping people busy. Self-sacrifice has direct positive consequences for the operation of the business. The way employees express their view of the company and the level of commitment they show to the

organization are crucial factors in deciding the level of leadership involvement (Turner et al., 1987). The views, attitudes, norms, values, and actions of the employees towards the organization are related to the performance of the leaders in that company (Hogg, 2001). Because leaders are also members of the organization and the many groups that exist within the company, they have at least one thing in common with employees that they manage leading. Leadership procedures have been implemented within the framework of the organization's membership, and indeed the qualifications of leaders as members of the organization play a key role in the effectiveness of leadership. The leader event organization handles ensuring that people are represented more effectively and efficiently (Yorges et al., 1999). As a result, the efficiency of the leader is evaluated using a variety of methods within the framework of subjective indicators, including objective financial criteria , sales, profit rates, return on investment, market share or feedback from stakeholders (Procházka & Smut, 2011). As a result of these qualities of the concept of leader effectiveness, in addition to company performance and strategy, it is necessary to investigate the effects of information sharing behavior within the company on business performance and the connections between them.

8. Behavior Regarding Information Sharing

Information exchange is one of the areas where the organization offers the most aid to its members in their efforts to achieve its goals. The organization's ability to coordinate the management of its resources will be a crucial factor in deciding whether the knowledge and ability sharing plan will be successful. Information, which has become the most powerful tool in creating value, produces more value when distributed (Gurteen, 1999). Information sharing behavior is described by Srivastava et al. (2006) defined as "team members who exchange business ideas, information and advice with each other". The dissemination of knowledge is vital for increasing the competitiveness of a company (Jasimuddin, 2007). In addition, several firms are trying to set up incentive and reward systems to encourage employees to share their ability (Bartol & Srivastava,

2002). However, we believe that effective leadership has the potential to motivate employees to share their knowledge. This is because effective leadership encourages employees to share their knowledge by developing a sense of unity and belonging within an organization, through the selfless efforts of the leader. In addition, effective leadership encourages employees to work together more effectively within an organization (Bartel, 2001; Kramer, 2006). An employee will constantly consider the interests of his company and the needs of his colleagues, which will motivate them to collaborate and share knowledge (Jasimuddin et al., 2006). Employees who find closely with their company are therefore more likely to share ability for the benefit of the organization. According to Janissary and Demirel (2007), it is more important for organizations to share their knowledge than to have information resources within the company. Indeed, information exchange can take place not only between two people, but also between an individual and a group, between groups, or between a person and a group or another individual (Msrdal, 2006). The concept of "knowledge sharing" can be simplified to mean making information accessible to different personnel within an organization. It is a common belief that if knowledge is given and used by various people, it can be renewed and transformed into a different form by increasing its intrinsic value (Chatlerina et al., 2018). The primary consequence of sharing each other's knowledge is the generation of new knowledge within the enterprise.

9. Finding Solutions to Current Challenges or Developing New Products for the Company

Knowledge is needed for the company to find solutions to existing challenges or to develop new products (Smith et al., 2006). Information exchange is beneficial not only for businesses, but also for workers working in such businesses (Estrada et al ., 2016). Sharing one's ability, serving the goal of validating, and supporting the knowledge one already has are functions that individual serve. In other words, the person evaluates his/her own knowledge in the light of the information obtained from the other individual as a direct result of sharing (Das et al ., 2017). The self-

evaluation ability of knowledge serves as the basis for this evaluation process. It also gives people the opportunity to address the misunderstandings and misconceptions they have about the facts and information that form the basis of their knowledge (Teixeira et al., 2018). In addition, the act of sharing one's knowledge with others allows various pieces of information to interact with each other, resulting in the production of added information and an increase in the general knowledge level of the individual (Barutçugil, 2002). As a result of these theories, it is necessary to explore the behavior of knowledge sharing, the leader influence, and the inter-variable influence and links between the outputs of the organization (business performance, firm performance, and company strategy).

When it comes to businesses, performance is extremely important. Because the productivity of an organization's workforce is the most crucial factor that decides its overall success (Ol, 2008). Employees manage their own performance appraisal, which is used to evaluate not only the current success level of the employees, but also their potential for future growth over a given period (Uyargil, 2013). Businesses have a better chance of achieving their goals if they conduct employee recruitment in a methodical manner and ensure that performance evaluation strategies and practices are implemented effectively (Palmer & Winters, 1993). Giving a person a reward based on their performance can push them to pay more attention to their work and approach tasks in a unique way. This will allow the individual to perform well and prove their ability more effectively.

10. Changes in the Structure of an Organization

Changes in the structure of an organization have often been associated with adverse effects on the health of the workforce (Oreg et al., 2011). Large-scale organizational changes, such as company restructuring, downsizing, and outsourcing, have been associated with physical and mental health complaints, absence, and prolonged sick leave (Kivimaki et al., 2001; Bamberger et al., 2012). These findings were discovered by researchers in Finland and the United States. On the other hand,

extensive knowledge studies are still underway as to why organizational changes are linked to adverse health outcomes. Clarifying the impacts of organizational change on workplaces and workers is a critical first step in reducing the negative health consequences of change and promoting change that is both healthy and effective. Previous meta-analytical studies have shown that a wide variety of psychological and social work factors, such as leadership, role conflict and ambiguity, job demands, control, and job insecurity, can predict employee well-being, health, and sick leave (Viswesvaran et al., 1999; Stansfeld and Candy, 2006). ; Nahrgang et al., 2011; Lang et al., 2012; Schyns and Schilling, 2013; Virtanen (Schuler and Jackson, 2001; Hoag et al., 2002).

It aimed to elucidate the effects of various organizational changes that occurred both separately and together and were repeated over time, to shed light on whether the extensive company change affected central aspects of psychosocial work. This was done so that it could be decided whether the extensive company change was affecting central aspects of the psychosocial work environment.

11. Organizational Change

The term "organizational change" refers to changing the structures, tactics, and processes of organizations as well as their culture (Quattrone & Hopper, 2001). The technique by which this happens is called the "how," and the essence of what is being transformed is called "what." Both aspects are included in the definition of the word. The transition from one condition to another is the change according to the dictionary meaning of the word. This change may be less deliberate, perhaps because of developments beyond the organization's control, or it may be deliberate to gain or lose certain characteristics of the organization to achieve a defined goal. In either case, this change can be carried out in one of two ways: also, other elements of the organization may be accidentally affected during the change process. This is especially true when people perceive change as excessive (Stensaker et al., 2001). Such undesirable reflections of organizational change

can have both positive and negative effects (Jian, 2007). They may be more likely to occur when multiple actions are needed to implement the change decision and many specialized problem-solving skills are needed (Casa & Lodge, 2015). In any case, organizational change is something new, something unknown and uncertain in nature, which can disrupt existing structures and processes within the organization and among its members. Thus, organizational change can be perceived as both an opportunity to win and a risk to lose and may involve redesigning tasks and responsibilities that alter the current job content and environment in many ways.

However, although earlier research has set up a link between organizational change and both physical and mental health (Vahtera et al., 1997; Kivimaki et al., 2001, 2003; Probst, 2003; Moore et al., 2004; Vahtera et al. 2004), much less is known about the effects of organizational change on psychosocial working conditions important to health.

A psychosocial work environment consists of organizational variables, social factors, and psychological factors that influence and decide the nature of many components of work, as well as the quality of these aspects (Nieuwenhuijsen et al., 2010). Formal and structural conditions such as employment contracts and work schedules are examples of organizational work factors.

These conditions decide how business is run within an organization. Relational characteristics of a workplace, such as the social environment and support from superiors and colleagues, are included in the category of social work factors. The term "psychological work items" refers to the characteristics of an individual job, such as perceived degrees of autonomy, job responsibilities, and job predictability. Earlier research has found a relationship between an organization's psychosocial working conditions and both employee and organizational outcomes (Stansfeld & Candy, 2006; Holden et al., 2011). These results include things like worker health (Lau and Knardahl, 2008; Vaananen et al., 2008; Bambra et al., 2009; Hausser et al., 2010; Nahrgang et al., 2011; Schmidt et al. (Dollard and Neser, 2013; Dysvik). and Kuvaas, 2013; Poulsen et al., 2016;

Montano et al ., 2017. Although it is common knowledge that organizational change has the potential to disrupt various organizational systems in addition to the health of employees, this still is true.

There appears to be few studies evaluating the effects of organizational change on certain aspects of the psychosocial work environment that are known to be health related.

- *Job duties (such as job control and job demand),*
- *Job roles (such as role clarity and role conflict),*
- *Leadership (such as fair, empowering, and supportive leadership),*
- *Social aspects (eg, employees and social climate) and*
- *Predictability (job predictability, future employability).*

12. Conclusion

In addition to routine, day-to-day operations, the organization must perform various tasks related to the change implemented while it is doing so. Kiwikiki et al. (2001) this can result in an increase in the total amount of work employees have to do and their job responsibilities. Because management needs to exercise control over the planning and execution process, there may be less room for employees to influence their work as in the past. As a result, employees' feelings of how much control they have over their jobs may change throughout the process (Paulsen et al., 2005). Thus, organizational change may be linked to higher job demands (i.e., demands for quantity and time of work) and a decrease in job control (i.e., influence on choices that affect one's responsibilities, co-workers, and clients). When significant changes occur within an organization, one of the most common consequences of such changes is the reorganization of the roles and duties of business employees. Such reorganization can put workers in a position where they must deal with conflicting demands, a lack of resources to fulfill the extra responsibilities assigned to them, or uncertainties about the goals and prospects of their new roles (Baillien and de Witte, 2009).

Thus, large-scale changes in the workplace can increase employees' feeling of role conflict (ie, competing demands and lack of resources) while at the same time reducing employee feeling of role clarity (i.e., clarity about roles' responsibilities and expectations). Following an organizational change, an employee's feeling of management and superiors may be affected by management's need to make difficult and sometimes unpopular decisions, such as downsizing or firing (Gilley et al., 2009; Holten & Brenner, 2015; Neves & Schyns, 2018). This is because the consequences of change can include the potential loss of valuable aspects such as certain duties, peer relationships, or even the existence of one's job. In addition, management-initiated changes started by external forces such as market demands, or technological innovation may also leave less room for employee involvement in decision-making and planning.

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